

MATERIALS FOR TEACHING CULTURE REALIA, FILMS, SIGNS

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Abstract: The culture of teaching and learning refers to the beliefs and value system in which both educators and learners value the process of teaching and learning, where their practices reflect their commitment and where the resources to facilitate teaching and learning are made available (Davidoff & Lazarus, 1997:43). Below we will examine how realia, film and signs relate to the study of culture.

Key words: culture, realia, movie, films, signs, symbol, cultural symbols, emblems, hand gestures, flags, animals.

The use of authentic materials in an EFL classroom is what many teachers involved in foreign language teaching have discussed in recent years. We have heard persuasive voices insisting that the English presented in the classroom should be authentic, not produced for instructional purposes. Generally, what this means is materials which involve language naturally occurring as communication in nativespeaker contexts of use, or rather those selected contexts where standard English is the norm: real newspaper reports, for example, real magazine

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articles, real advertisements, cooking recipes, horoscopes, etc. Most of the teachers throughout the world agree that authentic texts or materials are beneficial to the language learning process, but what is less agreed is when authentic materials should be introduced and how they should be used in an EFL classroom.

Realia is simply put realia refers to authentic objects from real life that one uses in the classroom to teach a specific concept. Realia can be both physical and virtual, as long as it is something used in the real world

Realia for ESL can make the learning experience more memorable and create connections between objects and vocabulary words or other language concepts.

This can make it easier to recall information. Realia reinforces language skills and appeals to both visual and kinesthetic learners of all ages. Most teachers use realia to demonstrate the meaning of vocabulary words.

As all we know, knowing a language goes beyond the knowledge of grammatical rules, vocabulary items and pronunciation of these items. Successful language learning requires language users to know that culture underlying language in order to get the meaning across. Also, Tseng (2002) suggests that culture effects changes in individual perception and is vital for expanding an individual's perspective of the world. Learning about the lived culture of actual target language speakers as well as about one's own culture requires tools that assist language learners in negotiating meaning and understanding the communicative and cultural texts in which linguistic codes are used" (p. 432). Also, Shanahan (1997, p. 168) states that cultural content provides exposure to living language that a foreign language student lacks. So, culture is not something consisting of facts to be learnt, but a helpful tool to make learners feel the need to speak and

use the target language.

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